

ISic0645

I.Sicily inscription 0645

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

cippus

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)**Place of origin (modern)**

Acate

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI332958

1. ἐνθάδε τίς; Μον-
2. τανὸς ἰητῆρ ἦδε γε-
3. ωργὸς ν | ὀκτω[κ]εικ[ο]-
4. σέτης κεῖτο μινυνθά-
5. διοσ, ν | κουριδίην ἄλο-
6. χον προλιπῶν καὶ νή-
7. πια τέκνα | καὶ γε-
8. νέτας ὀλοφυρο-
9. μένους πολιὰς τε
10. ἐθείρας | δρυπτο-
11. μένους, ὅτι οἱ νεο-
12. θηλέα καλὰ γέγι-
13. α ν | θυμὸν ἀπο-
14. πνείοντος ἐκέι-
15. ροσαν ἐν δακρύ-
16. οισιν. ν | Μοντα-

17. νόσ εὐσεβίη πα-
18. τήρ ἐποίησεν. ν
19. □ □
- 20.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644887

EDCS 71000789

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Bibliography

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